

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of D-Ribose by Quinquevalent Vanadium**

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The rate of oxidation of D-ribose with quinquevalent vanadium has been found to be first order both with respect to oxidant and substrate. The rate has been also found to depend on the first power of $[H^+]$ in 2.5M–4.5M acid range ; whereas the dependence was on the second power of $[H^+]$ in acid range >4.5M. The thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated as $\Delta E = 2.08 \pm 0.60$ K. cal/mole and $\Delta S^\ddagger = 8.0 \pm 0.1$ e. u. A positive salt effect and inverse dependence of rate on dielectric constant of the medium has been also observed. A mechanism involving C–C bond fission and via free radical has been proposed.

THE oxidation of carbohydrates in general and mono saccharides in particular has been studied by many workers¹⁻⁴. Amongst the transition metal ions used for the oxidation studies, quinquevalent vanadium is a versatile and potent oxidant. Recently Tripathi⁵ has studied the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of aldo and keto hexoses by this oxidant. The aldopentoses have been studied earlier by oxidants as Br_2 water in alkaline medium¹⁰, chloramine T¹¹ and $Cu(II)$ ¹². The present work is an attempt to study the oxidation of D-ribose by vanadium(V) in some details.

Experimental

Chemicals and Solutions : D-ribose (E. Merk), ammonium meta vanadate (Reidel, sulphuric and perchloric acids (AnalaR B.D.H. grade) and ferrous ammonium sulphate (B.D.H.) were used in this kinetic study. N-phenyl anthranilic acid was used as redox indicator, Sodium sulphate, sodium perchlorate, chromotropic acid etc. used were of AnalaR B.D.H. grade. For testing free radical formation during the course of the reaction acrylyn-H (Asian Acrylates, Bombay) was used.

Kinetic Measurements : Solutions of vanadium (V) and acid of requisite concentration were kept in a glass stoppered pyrex reaction flask for attaining constant temperature in a thermostatic bath ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). D-ribose stock solution which was prepared fresh always was also kept in a separate flask in the same thermostat. A known volume of D-ribose solution of requisite concentration was mixed with oxidant and acid solution in the reaction flask quickly to give a total of 30 ml. reaction mixture. Aliquots (2 ml.) of reaction mixture were withdrawn at suitable intervals and quenched in crushed ice bath. The unused vanadium(V) was titrated with standardised ferrous ammonium sulphate solution by using N-phenyl anthranilic acid as indicator.

Stoichiometry and Product Analysis : Stoichiometry of the reaction was studied by taking the substrate in excess as well as by taking the oxidant in excess ; the former to judge the reaction steps during kinetic runs and the latter to judge the overall oxidation products. The equivalents of oxidant per mole of substrate in the two cases have been found to be 2 and 10 respectively. Thus, the reaction under condition of kinetic run can be represented as :

On the other hand the overall reaction with excess oxidant proceeds further to oxidise the formed formaldehyde also and hence the reaction is

Formation of formaldehyde was confirmed by testing the sample under study during the course of reaction by usual tests with β naphthol and resorcinol, and also with chromotropic acid spot test. After the completion of reaction, the reaction mixture was distilled at $\sim 102^\circ$ and in this distillate the presence of formic acid was confirmed with mercuric chloride. The free radical formation during the course of reaction was confirmed by the induced polymerisation reaction of acrylyn-H monomer.

Results and Discussion

The rate studies were performed by taking D-ribose and sulphuric acid in sufficient excess over the oxidant concentration. The rate of disappearance of vanadium(V) was then observed experimentally to show the first order dependance of rate on vanadium(V) concen-

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tration (Table 1). The order of reaction with respect to D-ribose was also found to be one (Table 2). Effect of H⁺ concentration was studied in perchloric acid medium at constant ionic strength maintained by sodium perchlorate. It was found that rate is proportional to [H⁺] in lower acid range of 2.0 M to 4.5 M. While it is proportional to [H⁻]² in higher acid range (Table 3).

ranges. Thus, water molecule acts as a proton transferring agent¹⁷ in first case. So the following equilibria is operative¹⁵ in 2.5–4.5M acid range.

TABLE 1—TYPICAL KINETIC RUN

Time × 10 ³ sec.	Temp. 40°									
	[D-ribose] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻¹ M, [V(V)] = 9.0 × 10 ⁻³ M, [H ⁺] = 3.5 M, [μ] = 3.51 M									
Titre reading (a - x) ml.	0	18	36	54	72	90	108	126	144	
log a/a - x	8.55	6.95	5.90	5.00	3.90	3.10	2.55	2.00	1.65	
k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec. ⁻¹	—	0.09	0.16	0.23	0.34	0.44	0.52	0.63	0.71	
	—	1.15	1.03	0.99	1.09	1.13	1.12	1.07	1.14	
Average k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec. ⁻¹ = 1.09 ± 0.05										

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF RATE WITH [D-RIBOSE]

D-ribose × 10 ⁻¹ M	Temp. 40°				
	[V(V)] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M, [H ⁺] = 3.5 M, [μ] = 3.51 M				
k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec. ⁻¹	1.0	1.25	1.50	1.76	2.0
k ₁ [D-ribose]	0.98	1.29	1.46	1.72	1.91
k ₂ × 10 ⁴ LM ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹	9.80	9.60	9.73	9.83	9.55
Average k ₂ × 10 ⁴ = 9.70 ± 0.10 LM ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹					

In 5.0 M—6.5 M acid range the following equilibria¹⁸, in which the dependence is on 2nd power of [H⁺], is operative.

A primary salt effect was observed when the effect of ionic strength on rate was studied by varying it by sodium perchlorate (Table 4). The rate was also found to show an increase with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium, which was varied by using acetic acid water (30–70%) mixtures. These effects of ionic strength and the observed increase in rate with decrease in dielectric constant clearly indicate the involvement of these positively charged reactive species (shown in Step 1 and 2), which are active in rate determining step.

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF RATE WITH THE CONCENTRATION OF HYDROGEN ION

[D-ribose] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻¹ M	[V(V)] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M				
	[μ] = 4.51 M, Temp. 40°				
[H ⁺] M	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.0	4.5
k ₂ × 10 ⁴ LM ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹	15.89	19.04	21.29	26.46	28.63
k ₂ /[H ⁺] ² = k' ₂ × 10 ⁴ LM ⁻² sec. ⁻¹	6.36	6.35	6.08	6.61	6.36
Average k ₂ × 10 ⁴ = 6.35 ± 0.11 L ² M ⁻² sec. ⁻¹					
[μ] = 6.51 M, Temp. 30°					
[H ⁺] M	5.0	5.5	6.0	6.5	
k ₂ × 10 ⁴ LM ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹	25.32	44.20	57.03	78.40	
k ₂ /[H ⁺] ² = k' ₂ × 10 ⁴ L ² M ⁻² sec. ⁻¹	1.01	1.39	1.58	1.81	
Average k' ₂ × 10 ⁴ = 1.45 ± 0.25 L ² M ⁻² sec. ⁻¹					

TABLE 4—VARIATION OF RATE WITH IONIC STRENGTH.

[D-ribose] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻¹ M	Temp. 40°				
	[V(V)] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M, [H ⁺] = 3.5 M				
[μ] M	3.51	4.51	5.01	5.51	6.01
k ₂ × 10 ⁴ L ² M ⁻² sec. ⁻¹	5.27	6.01	6.70	7.44	8.03

In earlier studies for the rate of oxidation of organic compounds^{18,14,15} have indicated the dependence on [H⁺] for a particular reaction to be different under ranges due to different active oxidant species.¹⁶

The values of k₂ vary linearly with [H⁺] and [H⁻]² respectively in the two acid ranges. Nature of the plots (not given) indicate that only protonating species of vanadium(V) are active in both ranges. Water involvement is evident from the Zücker-Hammett (slope < 1.0) and Bunnett plots (w = 8.00 and 2.85) in both

The data (Table 5) of rate variation with temperature satisfied the Arrhenius equation.

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE.

Temp. °C	[D-ribose] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻¹ M, [V(V)] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M, [H ⁺] = 3.5 M, [μ] = 3.51 M				
	k ₂ × 10 ⁴ L ² M ⁻² sec. ⁻¹	1.94	2.79	5.66	9.19

The thermodynamic parameters evaluated were, $\Delta E = 20.8 \pm 0.60 \text{ K, cal/mole}$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -8.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ e.u.}$

The C-C bond fission¹⁹ appears to be involved in the rate determining step producing free radical and HCHO as given below (Equation 3(a) for lower Acid range and 3(b) for higher acid range).

or in general we can write it as

where R is CHO.CHOH.CHOH.CHOH

Rate determining step 3 does not involve a complex of V(V) and ribose as graph if plotted between k_1 and [D-ribose] passes through origin.

The free radical R' in further fast steps breaks into HCHO and HCOOH as under :

where $k''' \gg k'$ or k'' or k .

The reaction can proceed further also oxidising the formaldehyde molecules formed as shown below :

On the basis of above proposed mechanism steps the rate expression can be written now as below (details of derivation avoided for the sake of brevity).

For acid range $\leq 4.5 \text{ M}$

$$-\frac{d[\text{V(V)}]}{dt} = 2k'k''K_1[\text{VO}_2^+][\text{H}_3\text{O}^+][\text{C}_5\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5] \quad (A)$$

for acid range $> 4.5 \text{ M}$

$$-\frac{d[\text{V(V)}]}{dt} = 2k'k''K_2[\text{VO}_2^+][\text{H}^+]^2[\text{C}_5\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5] \quad (B)$$

The equations (A) and (B) explain the observed experimental data.

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